

DISTINCTIVE FEATURES OF THE GLOBALIZATION OF MORALITY AND RELIGION

Shaxnoza Murataliyevna Xaydarova

Mathematics Teacher

“Temurbeklar School” Military-Academic Lyceum, Fergana

ORCID ID: 0009-0005-9392-6754

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Abstract: In the article, the theoretical foundations of the study of the dialectical relationship between moral and religious values in the era of globalization, the dialectical analysis of the dialectical relationship between moral and religious values in the era of globalization, the problems and solutions of the future relationship of moral and religious values in the era of globalization are studied. Also, the genesis of the concept of moral and religious values, scientific-conceptual bases are analyzed.

Key words: era of globalization, moral and religious values, dialectic, dialectical attitude, social norms, moral outlook, national and universal values, principle of morality, harmony of values, globalization of morality and religion.

Introduction

Religion is an unparalleled social factor that calls humans to virtue, enriches their spiritual world, and ensures a moral environment. The history of the relationship between religion and morality dates back millennia. Even in the globalized world, religion continues to serve, to some extent, in ensuring morality in societal development. Both religious and secular factors remain important for societal progress today. Considering the current role of religion in social life, international relations, and cultural life, it should be noted that religion will continue to be a factor encouraging people towards mutual harmony, peace, and virtue.

Literature review and methods

The study of the relationship between morality and religiosity has long been a relevant task. Opinions on resolving this issue have been presented in the works of many thinkers. Historically, in social thought, morality and religiosity have been understood as mutually opposed, contradictory principles. Consequently, this conflicting perspective has played a decisive role in the understanding of their interrelationship. These issues have been researched by scholars such as I.V. Ponkin, S.D. Lebedev, K. Bagayeva, L. Syukiyaynen (Russia), G. Kremer, V. Shnayder-Deters, T. Nagel, V. Bader (Germany), H. Yavuz, S. Ershohin (Turkey), F. Kitcher, V. Furnyo (USA), A. Abdulla (Egypt), as well as A. Boynazarova, M. Abdurazzakova, Z. Minovarov, A. Qodirov, and A. Mo'minov.

Results and discussion

As social life develops and advances, we witness almost all aspects of our environment becoming globalized in a certain sense. Globalization processes affect not only the political and economic spheres of society but also its social and spiritual dimensions. Various forms of social consciousness acquire a new essence and manifest in entirely different ways. Currently, all changes and intensification of processes are collectively referred to as “globalization.” Before discussing the impact of this phenomenon on the relationship between morality and religion—the object of our study—it is appropriate to briefly answer the question: “What is globalization?”

One of the distinctive features of the era of globalization is that the entire world becomes a unified system; events occurring in one part of the world affect and resonate in other parts. Furthermore, the prosperity, development, or crisis of any state occurs not only in connection with neighboring countries but also with other regions and territories, making it impossible to remain isolated from this objective process. Remaining outside the globalization process (which is practically impossible) is tantamount to creating artificial obstacles to national development. The philosophical analysis of this axiom is that the decision to join or not join the globalization process cannot be made by a single nation, people, or the president or government of a state. Overall, when studying globalization and its features, it is not appropriate to evaluate this process as either positive or negative; rather, it is more purposeful to examine the unique characteristics of globalization and to understand the globalized world.

There is no social process, institution, or geographical region untouched by globalization. In the globalization era, just as in all forms of social consciousness and activity, morality and religion are also becoming globalized. Their internal structures and the functions they fulfill in social life have undergone qualitative changes, and this process is ongoing. Studying the globalization of morality and religion is one of the important aspects of investigating the current peculiarities of their interrelationship. This raises a pertinent question: what is the globalization of morality? Which aspects of the moral system does the globalization phenomenon affect, and what are the distinctive features of its manifestation? We will address these questions in detail.

A distinctive aspect of morality is that it occupies a place in the system of values of any society and that values are among the most important supports for adhering to moral norms. Morality is one of the key features distinguishing a particular region or social group from others. The globalization process is unlike

the traditional forms of manifestation of social consciousness. Today, the rapid flow of the globalization era significantly affects not only traditional and industrial but also post-industrial societies' social institutions. This process is directly observable in the globalization of morality as well. Within the context of globalization, the functional scope of morality and its principles is shrinking; traditional moral rules are increasingly replaced in the governance of society and regulation of social relations by "mass culture" based on risk, promoting immoral and frivolous lifestyles. Morality has begun to be reflected only in people's spiritual and moral spheres, while in the globalization era, values are primarily evaluated based on material needs and demands.

One of the most notable features of the globalization era is the emergence of specific moral norms in trade-economic and administrative-management social relations (for example, "the customer is always right," but only within certain limits; everything can be purchased except for items that are never sold, etc.). In other words, traditional moral views gradually lose their active position in social life and existing realities, leading to the emergence of a new form of global morality that meets the demands of the globalization era.

One of the most characteristic features of morality in the era of globalization is that, to date, the significance of regional specificities in the reflection of moral relations and norms in social life has considerably increased. There are certain reasons for this. In particular, the globalization process has, in turn, led to the emergence and development of anti-globalist movements opposed to this process. This is because globalization entails not only global opportunities, cooperation, and progress but also the global significance of problems and the increasing growth of global threats. This, in turn, can be illustrated by the social reflection of the famous third law of the English physicist I. Newton in mechanics, manifesting as anti-globalization processes. Anti-globalists advocate for protection against the effects of globalization, which has led to an intensification of the aspiration for national identity among ethnic groups living in some regions, and this has resulted in efforts to restore the system of customs and traditions formed over millennia, as well as an attempt to oppose the "mass culture" that forms the cultural context of globalization. A similar situation can also be observed in the example of our country.

As a result of this process, alongside the global significance of morality, localization is also observed. Certainly, we are far from the idea that this process has been fully realized in any particular region or ethnic group. However, the social and spiritual elites living in Eastern countries, having observed the example of Western countries, where economic development and rising living standards sometimes led to abandoning traditional moral norms with severe consequences, mostly advocate for state-level policies aimed at the stable development of moral norms (whether based on religious grounds or rational knowledge).

The Russian researcher M. Reshetnikov attempts to substantiate the primary role of information technologies in the emergence and development of globalization, viewing the main driving force of globalization as "the development of high technologies, the increase in the speed of information transmission, and the increasing complexity of its forms." The informatization process is one of the characteristic features of the globalization era. It is impossible to imagine today's world without the internet, cyberspace, and the virtual relationships of people within it. It is precisely in social relations in cyberspace that moral norms are being transformed, and spiritual and moral values are being reassessed.

It is important to emphasize that the emergence of world religions in the process of social development is considered one of the earliest forms of globalization. The process of globalization predates the term itself by centuries, with its socio-historical roots dating back several hundred years in human history. The globalization of religion can be directly associated with the emergence of world religions. Indeed, world religions are religions that are not limited to belief based on a particular region, race, or ethnic basis and are widespread worldwide. The concept of "world religion" refers to a social institution with a significant number of adherents globally and is not connected to any specific ethnonational or political unity. In other words, world religions are religions that concern all people universally and were the first manifestations of religious globalization. The ongoing globalization of religion remains characteristic, especially for the present day.

In recent years, one of the globally significant aspects in the religious sphere has been changes occurring in human consciousness. It is well known that religion is one of the phenomena expressed as a worldview that directs and regulates human consciousness.

Conclusion. At this point, it is necessary to emphasize that the freedom of information transmission and reception is one of the causes of changes occurring in religious consciousness. Furthermore, two tendencies can be distinguished in these changes. The first is connected to the improvement of conditions for the exercise of freedom of belief and conscience, which has led to a unique religious revival process worldwide. Consequently, each religion and confession is gaining broad opportunities to widely spread its beliefs, increase the number of its followers, restore, develop, and express religious traditions, customs, and ceremonies. This can be illustrated by the changes in the lives of peoples who, having overcome the consequences of atheistic regimes, are restoring their ancient religious values, as well as by integration processes occurring within various religions.

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